

TENSILE PROPERTIES AND POISSON'S RATIO OF PET NEEDLE-PUNCHED NONWOVEN FABRIC PREPARED BY THERMOCOMPRESSSION BONDING

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Introduction

Under-cover of vehicles

- Improving the fuel economy during high-speed driving
- Reducing noises generated due to chipping, sanding, and road noises from the road surface by minimizing the air resistance at the bottom of the vehicle body
- Improving the performance and service life of the vehicle by protecting the components therein, such as engines and transmissions, which are exposed to the external environment at the bottom of the vehicle body

Issues of under-cover of vehicles

- Under-cover are vulnerable to breakage by external impact, because the intermediate layer is made of a highly brittle material.
- The low-weight epidermal nonwoven fabric layer on the surface of the material could tear by chipping while driving, thereby leading to issues such as the exposure of the glass fiber.

To address such issues

- Composites are being developed using needle-punched PET nonwoven fabric, which is a new alternative material that is lightweight, low-cost, and has excellent sound absorption performance and durability.

Experiment

Preparation of nonwoven fabric

- Mixing short fibers for heat-resistant crystalline binders (fineness: 6.5De, strength: 4.02 g/De, and melting point: 180.22 °C) and regular short fibers (RSFs, fineness: 6De and fiber length: 51 mm)

Results

Tensile test specimen of needle-punched PET nonwoven fabric; (a) TD tensile test specimen of thermocompressed needle-punched PET nonwoven fabric, (b) Condition of the fiber along the thickness direction before thermocompression forming, (c) Condition of fiber along plane direction before thermocompression forming, (d) Condition of fiber along plane direction after thermocompression forming

Displacement-force graphs of the specimens in each direction; (a) MD specimens, (b) TD specimens

Strain-stress graphs of the specimens in each direction; (a) MD specimens, (b) TD specimens

Displacement-strain graphs in each direction for the MD tensile load; (a) displacement-strain graph of the XY plane, (b) elastic region trend lines in the displacement-strain graph of the XY plane, (c) displacement-strain graph of the XZ plane, (d) elastic region trend lines in the displacement-strain graph of the XZ plane

Tensile tester and DIC system

Displacement-strain graphs in each direction for the TD tensile load; (a) displacement-strain graph of the XY plane, (b) elastic region trend lines in the displacement-strain graph of the XY plane, (c) displacement-strain graph of the YZ plane, (d) elastic region trend lines in the displacement-strain graph of the YZ plane

- Poisson's ratio linearly decreases as the displacement increases.
- The reduction rate of TD specimen is higher than that of the MD specimen, and the positive Poisson's ratio turns into a negative Poisson's ratio in the elastic region.

Conclusion

- With increasing out-of-plane displacement of the needle-punched PET nonwoven fabric, Poisson's ratio also decreased.
- However, while a previous study reported a positive strain in the direction (Z-axis) perpendicular to the tensile direction from the beginning, the strain of the nonwoven fabric in this study turned from negative to positive with increasing displacement.